

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

AN OVERVIEW ON *GRACILARIA FOLLIFERA*

Suvetha Karupanan^{*1}, Mazher Sultana²

¹Department of Marine Biotechnology, AMET University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

²Unit of Human Health and Environmental Biotechnology, Department of Advance Zoology and Biotechnology, Presidency College, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 31/01/2017

Available online
09/02/2017

Keywords

Invertebrates,
Antioxidants,
Metabolites,
Pharmaceutical Potential.

ABSTRACT

The marine environment provides a broad range of diverse habitats from which novel sources of natural products can be derived. Seaweed is a term applied to multi cellular, marine algae which are large enough to be seen by the eye unaided. Some can grow to up to 60 meters in length. Seaweeds are a food source for marine animals such as sea urchins and fishes, and are the base of some marine food webs. They also provide shelter and a home for numerous fishes, invertebrates, birds and mammals. Seaweeds or marine macro algae are potential renewable resource in the marine environment. It has been used as antioxidant, cardiovascular agent, antimutagen, anticoagulant, antimicrobial, antitumor agent. Majority of their antioxidant activity is due to flavones, isoflavones, flavonoids, anthocyanin, Coumarin, ligands, catechins and isocatechin. Seaweeds are rich in antioxidants such as carotenoids, pigments, polyphenols, enzymes and diverse functional polysaccharides.

Corresponding author

Suvetha Karupanan

Research Scholar, Department of Marine Biotechnology,
AMET University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.
suveshankar@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Suvetha Karupanan** et al. An Overview on *Gracilaria Follifera*. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. 2017;7(01).

Copy right © 2017 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Marine

Studies from around the world have shown that marine organisms produce a diverse array of metabolites with novel chemical structures and potent biological activities as well as other desirable properties [1].

Marine Organisms for Drug Discovery

- Life has originated from the oceans that cover over 70% of the earth's surface and contain highly ecological, chemical and biological diversity starting from microorganisms to vertebrates.
- The source of unique chemical compounds, which hold tremendous pharmaceutical potential.
- Sources emphasize on investigation of the marine ecosystem to explore numerous complex and novel chemical entities.
- The sources of new leads for treatment of many diseases such as cancer, AIDS due to HIV, inflammatory conditions and a large variety of viral like DNA and RNA virus, bacterial and fungal diseases.

Marine algae are among the most ancient members of the plant kingdom, and vital components of the ecosystem of marine life. These plants are abundant in coastal areas, usually anchoring themselves to a hard surface using specialized holdfast structures. These structures are not true roots, and there are also no true shoots, leaves, seeds, water conducting tissues, or flowers. Species can range in size from very small (3 -10 microns) to very large (over 200 feet long) and some can grow more than 10 inches per day. The three best known types of marine algae are red algae, green algae and brown algae was shown in figure 1 [2].

Figure 1: Structure of some marine algae.

Marine organisms are sources of highly bioactive secondary metabolites leads in development of new pharmaceutical agents.

Algae can be classified into two main groups

1. Microalgae - Blue green algae, Dinoflagellates, Diatoms
2. Macroalgae - Green, Brown and Red algae

Red algae are considered as the most important source of many biologically active metabolites in comparison to other algal classes. The most common name for marine algae is seaweed. Seaweeds are popularly described as plants, but it is not a true plant. Marine algae are mostly found in shallow ocean water near rocky shores. It is also found in fresh water, such as ponds, lakes and rivers [3]. The characters of algae are show in table 1.

Table 1: Characteristic future of some algae.

S. No	Unicellular	Multicellular	Example
Red Algae	Present	Present	<i>Gacillaria, Laurencia papillosa</i>
Brown Algae	Present	Present	<i>Turbineria ornata, Macrocystis</i>
Green Algae	Present	Present	<i>Ulva lactuca,, Codium</i>

Sea weeds

Seaweeds include members of the red, brown and green algae. They are members of the kingdom Protista meaning they are not Plants. They do not have the vascular system of plants and do not have roots, stems, leaves and flowers or cones. Like plants they use the pigment chlorophyll for photosynthesis but also contain other pigments some examples for algae

Brown Algae - Phaeophyta

GreenAlgae - Chlorophyta

Red Algae - Rhodophyta

Blue green algae

They are in a group called cyanobacteria and are more closely related to bacteria. Some cyanobacteria form brown, green, red or purple tufts on coral reefs. To survive seaweeds need salty or brackish water, sunlight and a surface to attach themselves to. Because of these factors they are generally found in the littoral zone. They are usually found on rocky rather than on sand or shingle shores [4].

Morphology of Seaweeds

Seaweeds do not require support structures. Instead of roots seaweeds have holdfasts, which attach them to the sea floor. A holdfast is not necessary for water and nutrient uptake, but is needed as an anchor. The stalk or stem of seaweed is called as stipe. The function of the stipe is to support the rest of the plant. The structure of the stipe varies among seaweeds and they can be flexible, stiff, solid, gas filled, very long, short or completely absent

The kelps form dense forests which support entire underwater communities providing both food and shelter. Intertidal seaweeds can be exposed to many environmental stresses including drying out when not under water, temperature and salinity changes and wave action [5].

Pharmacological Application of Marine Algae

Contains many inorganic and organic compounds benefit for mankind. Various compounds with biological activities are isolated and it possesses pharmacological activities such as antioxidant, antimicrobial, antiviral, anticoagulant, antitumor, anti-inflammatory, antihyperlipidemic and antihypertensive response.

GRACILARIA FOLLIFERA

Gracilaria is a genus of red algae notable for its economic importance as an agarophyte as well as its use as a food for humans and various species of shellfish. Various species within the genus are cultivated among Asia South America Africa and Oceania some species was shown in figure 2 [6].

Division : *Rhodophyta*
 Kelas : *Rhodophyceae*
 Genus : *Gracilaria*
 Spesies : *Gracilaria follifera*

Figure 2: *Gracilaria Follifera*.

Gracilaria follifera species are rare and their distribution is restricted. *Gracilaria follifera* was described from the Red Sea as *Fucus follifer* Forsk. Plants referable to this species are now reported from various parts of the world, including both the eastern and western coasts of the north Atlantic. However, little information is available on *Gracilaria follifera* from the British Isles, and in the present instance we have investigated the life history of this alga in culture together with preliminary results on growth in small-scale tanks with running sea water [7].

Plants of *Gracilaria edulis*, *Gracilaria follifera* is available mostly in station near Rameswaram (79° 19'E, 9°17' N), which is situated on the Palk Bay side at about 20 km east of Mandapam. *Gracilaria edulis* and *Gracilaria follifera* occur abundantly on dead coral stones in a shallow sublittoral lagoon [8].

From the data collected for two and a half years it is clear that similar changes occur in the growth of *Gracilaria edulis* and *Gracilaria follifera* year after year with two peak growth seasons per year [9].

Growth, reproduction and spore output in *gracilaria follifera*

Observations made for one year on the seasonal changes in growth, reproduction and spore output of *gracilaria folifera* are given. These red algae occurred only a few months during the year. Maximum growth of *Gracilaria follifera* was during April. Tetrasporophytes were more abundant than carposporophytes in *Gracilaria follifera* [10]. Maximum outputs of tetra spores and carpospores were recorded and the period of peak shedding of spores coincided with the peak growth period of these seaweeds. There was, however, no definite rhythm of diurnal spore output [11].

Life history and culture of *Gracilaria follifera*

Three species of *Gracilaria* are *Gracilaria follifera* Borg, *Gracilaria verrucosa* Papenf and *Gracilaria bursa bastoris*. In Britain *Gracilaria verrucosa* is widely distributed, although not common, whereas the other two species are rare and their distribution restricted. *Gracilaria follifera* was described from the Red Sea as *Fucus follifer* Forsk. Plants referable to this species are now reported from various parts of the world including both the eastern and western coasts of the north Atlantic [12]. However considerable variation exists within species of *Gracilaria*, thus delimitation of species is often extremely difficult. *Gracilaria follifera* from Britain is similar morphologically to the original material of *Fucus foliifer* as illustrated by Borgesen and therefore, we have limited our consideration to *Gracilaria follifera* as it occurs in Britain. However little information is available on *Gracilaria follifera* from the British Isles and in the present instance we have investigated the life history of this alga in culture together with preliminary results on growth in small-scale tanks with running sea water [13-15].

THE ARTIFICIAL CULTIVATION OF *GRACILARIA*

With the development of the agar-agar industry, the need for *Gracilaria* increased further. Experiments on artificial cultivation have been carried out in many countries in recent years, the stake net culture of *gracilaria asiatica* in the tidal zone [16].

China is the foremost country in *Gracilaria* culture. Remarkable achievements, especially along the southern coast of mainland and the western coast of Taiwan, have been reported. Two methods are chiefly used for artificial cultivation of *Gracilaria* in China. One is pond scattering culture and the other is raft culture of stake-rope culture [17]. The first method is most suitable for species from which spore lings are easy to obtain, it propagates vegetatively and can be harvested from time to time during the whole growing period. *Gracilaria parvaspora* and *gracilaria blodgettii* are other examples. They propagate through spores released now and then in spring, summer and autumn [18]. In this method, sporelings are cultured in seawater ponds, saline lakes or wasted salt pans. The procedures are easy. The second method is used to culture species which have good quality and high agar content, such as *gracilaria asiatica*, *gracilaria tenuistipitata*, *gracilaria gigas* and *gracilaria sjoestedtii*, etc. They propagate only through spores [19].

Artificial cultivation of *Gracilaria* is carried out by taking into account its biological characteristics. Suitable sites must be selected and effective measures must be adopted in order to get good results [20].

Selection of culture sites

A basic requisite in the selection of a site for the cultivation of *Gracilaria* is an understanding of the ecological factors required and culture method chosen. Generally, three types of cultivation sites exist, namely, areas inside bays, offshore regions and ponds [21].

Spore collection and sporeling culture

Spore collection and sporeling culture methods were derived gradually with the development of production. Two methods are used; one is used in the open sea, the other indoor [22, 23].

CONCLUSION

Marine algae are abundant in the oceans and it shows a rich source of secondary metabolites. *Gracilaria* is the raw material for the agar industry world-wide. Chile is the largest producer of *Gracilaria* and Japan is the largest producer of agar. World agar production is currently estimated at 10,000 tonnes per annum, about half of which is from *Gracilaria*. *Gracilaria* is used as a food in Japanese, Hawaiian and Filipino cuisine. In Philippines it is used to make gelatin also called *gulaman*. *Gracilaria* oligosaccharides with degree of polymerization 6 prepared by agarase digestion from agar-bearing *Gracilaria* sp. polysaccharides have been shown to be an effective prophylactic agent during *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments against Japanese encephalitis viral infection and some other non communicable diseases. In this review we found the pharmacological potential and chemical profiles of the *Gracilaria* species and it shows antimicrobial activity, antiviral, antihypertensive, antifungal, etc. Others referenced the cytotoxicity bioassays in which these algae species are not active, but they produce various types of prostaglandins and others substances that can be toxic to humans such as gastrointestinal disorders and lethality caused by some species of algae but no evidence against *Gracilaria species like verrucosa, edulis and follifera* respectively.

To research new drugs from the above species is necessary to evaluate other bioassay models to preserve the safety, efficacy and quality of the end products. From the above review we conclude that algae of the *Gracilaria* genus are a potential source for synthesis of new natural medicines.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Our special thanks to all staff of AMET University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, especially the Department of Marine Biotechnology and laboratory staff for their kind support and help in facilitating our study.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AIDS : Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome
 NSAID : Nonsteroidal Anti-inflammatory Drug
 RNA : Ribonucleic acid.
 DNA : Deoxy ribonucleic acid.
 HIV : Human immunodeficiency virus

REFERENCES

1. Cynthia LF and Heloia SF. Bioactivities from Marine Algae of the Genus *Gracilaria*. Int. J. Mol. Sci. 2011; 12(7): 4550-4573
2. Xavier DR, Shanmugavel S, Kuppu R, Sundaram J. Screening of selected marine algae from the coastal Tamil Nadu, South India for antibacterial activity. Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine. 2012; S140-S146
3. Seema P. Therapeutic importance of sulfated polysaccharides from seaweeds: updating the recent findings. Biotech. 2012; 2(3): 171-185.
4. Jigna C and Avani K. Antimicrobial compounds of marine algae from Indian coast. Int.J.Curr.Microbiol.App.Sci. 2014; 3(7): 526-532

5. Yu Y, Jiann C, et al. White Shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* That Have Received *Gracilaria tenuistipitata* Extract Show Early Recovery of Immune Parameters after Ammonia Stressing. *Mar Drugs*. 2015; 13(6): 3606–3624.
6. Goran MN, Florian W, Martin R. Metabolomic Assessment of Induced and Activated Chemical Defence in the Invasive Red Alga *Gracilaria vermiculophylla*. *PLoS One*. 2011; 6(12): 29359.
7. Masoumeh N, Soodabeh S and Ahmad R. Gohari Sterols from the red algae, *Gracilaria salicornia* and *Hypnea flagelliformis*, from Persian Gulf. *Pharmacogn Mag*. 2011; 7(26): 97–100.
8. Lavakumar V, Masilamani K, et al. Promising upshot of silver nanoparticles primed from *Gracilaria crassa* against bacterial pathogens. *Cent J*. 2015; 9: 42.
9. Chistiane O and Ricardo BS. Mechanisms Involved in the Anti-Inflammatory Action of a Polysulfated Fraction from *Gracilaria cornea* in Rats. *PLoS One*. 2015; 10(3): 0119319
10. Blunt JW and Copp BR. North cote and Prinsep MR. Marine natural products. *Nat. Prod. Rep*. 2005; 22: 15-61.
11. Smith AJ. Medicinal and pharmaceutical uses of seaweed natural products: A review. *J. Appl. Phycol*. 2004; 16: 245-262.
12. Hosokawa M, Bhaskar N, Sashima T and Miyashita K. Fucoxanthin as a bioactive and nutritionally beneficial marine carotenoid. *Carotenoid Sci*. 2006; 10: 15-28.
13. Davis AR, Targett NM, McConnell OJ, and Young CM. Epibiosis of marine algae and benthic invertebrates: natural products chemistry and other mechanisms inhibiting settlement and overgrowth. *Bioorg. Mar. Chem*. 1989; 3: 85-114.
14. Balakrishnan CP. Algal documentation and Phytochemical studies of red algae *Gracilariacorticata* of Manapad Coast, Tamil Nadu. *JPP*. 2013; 2(4): 193-197.
15. Meenakshisundaram et al. Anticancer Effects of Different Seaweeds on Human Colon and Breast Cancers. 2014; 23-29.
16. Rcher W. The Desmidiaceae of Norway, Bidrag till kannedomen om sydligare Norges Desmidieer. *Journal of Botany*. 1874; 12: 92-95.
17. McLachlan J and Edelstein T. Life-history and culture of *Gracilaria follifera*. *South Devon Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*. 1977; 57: 03.
18. Chitra G. Biochemical studies on selected macroalgae of thikkodi Coast, kerala. *Journal of international academic research for multidisciplinary*. 2015; 3: 9.
19. Lachlan J and Edelstein T. Life-history and culture of *Gracilaria follifera*. *South Devon*. 1997; 57(3): 577-586.
20. Kyaw A. The Production of *Gracilaria eduli* in Burma, Report of the Training Course on *Gracilaria* Algae. Manila, Philippines. 2013; 27: 1–30.
21. Davidson A. Seafood of South-East Asia: A Comprehensive Guide with Recipes. Ten Speed Press; 2004. 197.
22. Thomas J. Innovative Methods of Marine Ecosystem Restoration. CRC Press; 2013. 193.
23. Chennubhotla VN. Growth reproduction and spore output in *Gracilaria follifera* boergesen and *Gracilariopsis sjoestedtii* Dawson around Mandapam. *Indian Journal of Fisheries*. 2013; 33(1): 76-84.

54878478451170136

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

